

Different operationalizations of local research and their associated citation patterns: A study of African publications

Supplemental material

S1. Publications per country

Table S1 presents the distribution of publications by journal country. As shown, a few countries—particularly South Africa and Nigeria—account for a large share of the publication output. South Africa and Nigeria together represent over half of the dataset, with 32.9% and 23.9% of the publications, respectively. In contrast, the next country by volume, Uganda, accounts for only 7.9% of the total. Several countries, including Benin, Sierra Leone, Tunisia, Angola, and Botswana, contribute just 0.1% or less of the publications in the dataset.

Table 3. Number and percentage of AJOL publications per country

Country	n	%	Country	n	%
South Africa	13,844	32.9	Zambia	180	0.4
Nigeria	10,048	23.9	Rwanda	105	0.2
Uganda	3,339	7.9	Eswatini	98	0.2
Egypt	2,812	6.7	Côte d’Ivoire	88	0.2
Algeria	2,697	6.4	Sudan	77	0.2
Ethiopia	2,046	4.9	South Sudan	70	0.2
Kenya	1,547	3.7	Senegal	66	0.2
Cameroon	836	2.0	Burkina Faso	66	0.2
Ghana	693	1.6	Mauritius	65	0.2
Tanzania	480	1.1	Sierra Leone	41	0.1
Togo	425	1.0	Benin	27	0.1
Libya	270	0.6	Tunisia	22	0.1
Zimbabwe	248	0.6	Angola	21	<0.1
Malawi	190	0.5	Botswana	19	<0.1

S2. Publications per research area

Table S2 displays the number and percentage of publications by research area. As with the distribution by country, certain fields—most notably Medicine—account for a significantly larger share of the publications, representing 39.6% of the total. In contrast, other areas such as Veterinary Science, Energy, Physics and Astronomy, and Chemical Engineering each contributes less than 1% of the publications.

Table S2. Number and percentage of AJOL publications per research areas

Area	n	%	Area	n	%
Medicine	16,690	39.6	Immunology and Microbiology	1,299	3.1
Social Sciences	9,094	21.6	Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmaceutics	798	1.9

Agricultural and Biological Sciences	7,237	17.2	Chemistry	750	1.8
Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology	4,181	9.9	Decision Sciences	614	1.5
Health Professions	4,039	9.6	Earth and Planetary Sciences	584	1.4
Environmental Science	3,750	8.9	Materials Science	575	1.4
Engineering	2,857	6.8	Neuroscience	596	1.4
Arts and Humanities	2,818	6.7	Mathematics	548	1.3
Psychology	2,341	5.6	Dentistry	420	1.0
Economics, Econometrics and Finance	1,805	4.3	Veterinary	311	0.7
Business, Management and Accounting	1,732	4.1	Energy	275	0.7
Computer Science	1,690	4.0	Physics and Astronomy	166	0.4
Nursing	1,335	3.2	Chemical Engineering	62	0.1

S3. Percentage of publications per locality criteria

Table 5 shows the percentage of publications classified as local and non-local for each measure of local research for AJOL publications and the publications citing them. Due to missing values in certain fields (e.g., author affiliation), the percentages of local and non-local publications do not always sum to 100%. In such cases, the remaining proportion is classified as *Not Applicable* (NA) and excluded from the analysis. As a result, each locality criterion may include a different set of publications in the citation analysis, depending on data availability. The table highlights substantial variation in the number of publications identified as local across criteria. It also shows that in almost all cases, with a single exception, the number of non-local articles exceeds that of local ones.

Table S3. Percentage of publications classified as local or non-local according to each locality criterion*

	J WoS/Scopus		J title		Art title		All authors		Any author	
	Local	Non-local	Local	Non-local	Local	Non-local	Local	Non-local	Local	Non-local
AJOL pubs	34%	66%	28%	71%	12%	87%	31%	36%	37%	29%
Citing pubs	16%	84%	6%	94%	3%	94%	13%	69%	20%	62%

*Publications not included in either local or non-local are due to missing values and therefore classified as NAs.